

NETWORK INFRASTRUCTURE DESIGN OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL BUILDING, ISABELA SCHOOL OF ARTS AND TRADES (ISAT) ANNEX

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ABSTRACT - In response to challenges identified in the existing network infrastructure at ISAT Annex Senior High School, this study employed the Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate and Optimize (PPDIOO) model to propose a strategic network design. Utilizing Cisco Packet Tracer and Unifi Design Center, the research focused on a collapsed-core topology, emphasizing scalability, security, and efficient connectivity. Simulation testing and expert evaluations validated the proposed design, demonstrating successful Virtual Local Area (VLAN) Network implementation, extensive Wi-Fi coverage, and secure communication. The Network Infrastructure Design Questionnaire (NIDQ) assessment affirmed strong agreement on usability and feasibility. The study concluded with recommendations, urging the implementation of the proposed design, emphasizing security measures, reliable internet access, and network optimization. Future research was encouraged to explore 5G technology impact and emerging trends in network infrastructure.

Keywords: Network Infrastructure, PPDIOO Model, Cisco Packet Tracer, Simulation, Educational Network, Design, Optimization, Emerging Technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

As technology continues to play an increasingly important role in education, schools are facing new challenges and opportunities when it comes to leveraging digital tools and resources to enhance the learning experience.

Network infrastructure is a must to consider in every organization to cope with modernization and globalization. Network infrastructures are not only responsible for providing backbone connectivity, but also for ensuring utmost reliability in line with the security measures and standards that are widely accepted in the field of information and communications technology [1].

Network infrastructure in educational institutions provides several benefits, such as facilitating communication and collaboration between teachers and students, providing access to online resources, and enabling real-time feedback and support. However, managing and maintaining a network infrastructure in educational institutions is not without its challenges.[2] one of the key challenges is scalability, as schools and universities continue to grow and expand, the demand for network resources also increases. It is crucial to design a network infrastructure that can be easily

scaled up or down to meet changing needs. The limited nature of LANs means that they usually stay outside the regulations implemented by authorities. Hence, to efficiently manage and transfer information, the use of computers, databases, proper software along with installing an information network is essential. The information network must be configured in such a way that all users can easily and immediately access all information they need [3].

Protecting the network is also one of the problems in terms of internetworking in the design of campus networks [4]. Higher education institutions' administrators need to carefully implement and supervise network security measures to protect confidentiality, integrity and full-time availability of the computing resources that it supports [5]. Securing computer networks is a very extensive issue that involves a whole range of relatively separate areas, such as data encryption, firewalls, and the overall security policy of organizations, as noted by Balogh et al. (2018). Despite the many research and development activities in the field of data communications security, the importance of internal LAN security is still underestimated, and a security threat on any computer, based on a particular LAN attack, always comes from a compromised computer [6].

The networking configuration at ISAT-Annex has resulted in dissatisfaction among both students and staff due to frequent changes in IP addresses for each client, leading to connectivity issues. This has made it difficult for the SHS building to establish a reliable network connection and caused significant productivity losses for students who rely on online resources for course materials. Additionally, the lack of internet access in ISAT Annex's Computer Lab has further contributed to significant productivity losses for students who rely on online materials. [7] Providing stable internet connectivity is crucial in improving digital affordability, competencies, and confidence levels for students, leading to enhanced program delivery, improved learning engagement, and development.

Redesigning the LAN infrastructure of ISAT-Annex is necessary to provide stable and dependable connectivity and address issues such as scalability, network security, and limited internet access. A well-designed LAN infrastructure can offer several benefits, such as facilitating communication and collaboration, providing access to online resources, and enabling real-time feedback and support. Implementing proper security measures and providing stable internet connectivity can enhance students' digital competencies and confidence levels, leading to improved program delivery and enhanced learning engagement and development.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

LAN Infrastructure in Educational Institutions

In educational institutions, a Local Area Network (LAN) plays a critical role in facilitating information sharing and supporting the Teaching and Learning Process (TLP). LANs typically cover a small geographical area, such as an office, university, or home. Ethernet-based LANs are the most common type and include several wirings and signaling variants [8].

The need for a well-designed campus network that incorporates radio coverage for indoor and outdoor wireless networks [9]. The article proposes that the coverage of indoor wireless networks determines the number and points of access points (APs) and suggests that an optimal operating state for portable computers is achieved when the number of computers is between 20-30 and within a range of 35-110 meters. He also discusses the use of overlapping wireless coverage schemes to establish multiple wireless coverage base stations for achieving wireless coverage throughout the campus.

LAN Simulation and Testing

Simulation tools are essential for validating

research ideas before implementation across various fields [10]. Network simulators enable researchers to test the performance of algorithms and protocols. Some network simulation tools discussed include NS-2, NS-3, OMNET++, GloMoSim, QualNet, NetSim, JiST/SWANS, and J-Sim. Open source and commercial simulators are both discussed, with OPNET, GloMoSim, QualNet, NetSim, JiST/SWANS, and NS-3 preferred for simulating large networks, while NS-2 and J-Sim are better suited for small network simulations. Proper selection of a simulation tool depends on research requirements.

[11] Showed that computer network training is more effective through the use of Packet Tracer simulations. Packet Tracer, a software developed by Cisco, is widely used in computer networking education [12]. It offers simulation, visualization, authoring, collaboration, and assessment features, making it an effective tool for students to experiment and practice various network tasks. The software is also a part of the Cisco Networking Academy Program (CNAP), which uses it for teaching and learning computer network courses.

Synthesis:

Effective management and security of LANs in educational institutions were essential for facilitating information sharing and supporting the Teaching and Learning Process (TLP). Ethernet-based LANs were commonly used, dividing data into smaller frames and providing services up to the data link layer. To ensure secure internet access, implementing an extended access list on departmental routers was recommended. Additionally, a well-designed campus network with hierarchical architecture and radio coverage for wireless networks could enhance network performance. The choice of network topology was crucial for effective campus network management. Star topology was recommended for LAN networks in educational institutions due to its benefits such as easy reconfiguration, quick damage detection and prevention, and centralized management. Consideration could also be given to bus topology to improve network performance and mitigate high packet loss, but further research was necessary to assess its performance in various scenarios. Two-tier hierarchical network designs offered modularity, flexibility, Gigabit connectivity, and security features suitable for educational institutions.

Simulation tools, including Packet Tracer, NS-2, NS-3, OMNET++, GloMoSim, QualNet, NetSim, JiST/SWANS, and J-Sim, were valuable for validating research ideas and providing network training in the field of computer networking. Packet Tracer, widely used in educational settings, offered effective simulation and visualization capabilities,

empowering students to experiment and practice network tasks. The appropriate selection of a simulation tool should be based on research requirements and educational needs.

In conclusion, implementing recommended network topologies, security measures, and simulation tools significantly improved the management, performance, and security of LANs in educational institutions. These measures established a solid foundation for supporting the Teaching and Learning Process by ensuring secure and efficient access to information and resources.

III. DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Program Requirements:

Table 1 summarized the essential prerequisites for optimal performance, including the designated operating system, processor speed, memory capacity, and hard drive space. These specifications were especially important in terms of their use of Cisco Packet Tracer version 7.3.0, as they had a direct impact on the tool's compatibility and overall effectiveness in the research process.

Table 1. Minimum Hardware Requirements

Description	Specification
Operating System	Windows 8.1 or newer (64bit), Ubuntu 20.04 LTS (64bit) or macOS 10.14 or newer.
Processor	amd64(x86-64) CPU
RAM	2 GB or higher
Hard Disk Driver	1.4 GB of free disk space

Note: these requirements are specific to Cisco Packet Tracer version 7.3.0 and may differ for other versions.

The PPDIOO model was utilized by the researchers to design the proposed network infrastructure of ISAT Annex.

Figure 1. Modified Prototyping Methods

The Prepare, Plan, Design, Implement, Operate, and Optimize (PPDIOO) model was a structured technique for network design and management. However, the 'Implementation' phase was purposefully excluded for this study. The modification was required due to the nature of simulation-based research, which did not involve the

actual deployment of a network but instead focused on its operational features. The modified PPDIOO technique remained reliable; it began with extensive planning and preparation, then moved on to customized design, active network operation, and continuing optimization. This technique ensured that the study met its research objectives while considering the unique requirements of simulation-based research.

Prepare Phase:

In this phase, the researchers carefully gathered and analyzed essential data for the ISAT Annex network infrastructure design. They defined the network's goals and objectives, aligning them with the institution's strategic vision, while also identifying potential risks and challenges. This comprehensive approach offered a solid foundation for the subsequent project phases, ensuring the network design met current and future needs effectively.

Planning Phase

Based on the goals and objectives identified in the prepare phase, the researchers developed a detailed strategy for the ISAT Annex network infrastructure architecture.

Design Phase:

During this stage, the researchers carefully designed the layout, topology, and necessary hardware for the proposed network infrastructure at ISAT Annex, ensuring a simplified setting for the entire building. To protect the network from potential threats, strong security measures were also given priority in the design. It's important to be aware that the PLDT Home's 400 Mbps Fiber Unli Plan 2099, which was chosen to meet the required bandwidth requirements, might have been subject to price changes. The researchers monitored and assessed the initiative's cost-effectiveness throughout.

Operate Phase:

The researchers simulated the proposed network infrastructure design of ISAT Annex through Cisco Packet Tracer. They operated the simulated network and provided support to users. They also monitored the network performance and made adjustments as necessary to ensure its smooth operation.

Optimize Phase:

In this phase, the researchers assessed the ISAT Annex LAN simulation, pinpointing areas that required improvement. They then proceeded to make essential adjustments and optimizations to enhance the overall performance and efficiency of the network, ensuring it remained aligned with the evolving needs of ISAT Annex

Respondents of the Study

To determine the required number of respondents, the researchers used a reliable method. As such, they considered a sample size of twelve (12) appropriate for the research.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Respondents

Respondent	Frequency	Percentage
IT Experts	11	91.66 %
ICT Coordinator	1	8.33%
Total	12	100%

Sampling Technique

This study used the stratified random sampling technique to ensure a representative sample from each sub-group of the population. This method selected a representative sample from each stratum of the population.

In order to select a representative sample from each stratum of the population, the following formula was used for the stratified sampling technique:

$$= \left(\frac{\quad}{\quad} \right) \times$$

where:

= the sample size for stratum i

= the population size for stratum i

= the total population sizes

= the desired sample size for the entire population

Statistical Treatment

The Likert Scale was used to interpret the items in the questionnaire and to obtain the overall evaluation result of the proposed network infrastructure design of ISAT Annex.

Table 3. Statistical Interpretation of Data

NUMERICAL SCALE	RANGE	INTERPRETATION
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree

The data that were gathered were analyzed to determine the weighted mean with the following formula:

$$h = \frac{(\cdot)}{\quad}$$

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Problems encountered in the existing network configuration of ISAT Annex

The existing network architecture within the Senior High Building at ISAT Annex features a straightforward design, incorporating three unmanaged switches in each computer lab. These unmanaged switches facilitate connections for 14 client devices and 1 server in each lab, resulting in a total of 42 client connections and 3 server connections per lab. This configuration, while basic, establishes a functional network infrastructure within the labs. The accompanying network map outlines the relationships among thin clients, servers, and unmanaged switches. Notably, only one computer lab is equipped with a router, but despite this, internet access remains unavailable. Additionally, the entire building lacks both internet access and WiFi connectivity.

The Existing Network Configuration

In analyzing the current network configuration, several aspects come under scrutiny, including the Physical Layout, Network Map, IP Addressing Structure, Network Security and Processes, and Devices connected in the network. Each of these components contributes to the overall functionality and efficiency of the network infrastructure within the Senior High Building at ISAT Annex. Examining these elements provides a comprehensive understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of the existing setup, paving the way for targeted improvements and enhancements.

Proposed Network Infrastructure Design

The researchers proposed a network infrastructure design tailored for ISAT Annex's Senior High School Building, aiming to address current challenges and enhance efficiency. The design incorporates a collapsed-core topology, strategically placing Wi-Fi access points on the second floor for comprehensive building coverage. Security measures, including VLANs and port security, were implemented to ensure a secure network environment. PLDT Home's 400 Mbps Fiber Unli Plan 2099 was recommended to meet bandwidth requirements. Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), VLAN Trunking Protocol (VTP), and Quality of Service (QoS) methods were utilized to optimize IP assignment and network performance.

Simulation Testing and Result

This section explores simulation test results, offering a comprehensive assessment of the proposed ISAT Annex senior high building network design. It unveils insights into functionality, security, and overall efficiency within the simulated environment, revealing practical implications and

potential refinements

VLAN Efficiency

VLANs are used in proposed network design to efficiently organize and isolate segments, reducing congestion and improving communication. VLANs help to improve network performance while also increasing security by reducing the risk of unauthorized access.

Figure 2. PC 7 Initiating ARP Request

Figure 3. VLAN-Restricted ARP Broadcast by the Switch

Figure 2 shows PC 7 sending out an ARP request to find PC 8's MAC address. The switch in Figure only broadcasts this ARP request to the ports connected to the VLAN that contains PC 8. This demonstrates how VLANs effectively control network traffic by reducing congestion through focused broadcasts inside the designated VLAN.

Wi-Fi and Security Cameras Coverage Simulation Results

Access Points were carefully installed on the second floor to ensure reliable internet connectivity at Senior High building, offering optimal coverage for the whole three-story building. This arrangement ensures continuous internet connectivity, fulfilling both students' and faculty's educational demands.

Figure 4. Wi-Fi Coverage of Senior High Building

Note: The illustration tool may not fully show access points' diameter range, so the depicted coverage is limited to the second floor. The strategic placement of access points on this floor aims to

ensure comprehensive coverage for the entire building.

Figure 5. Security Camera Coverage of Senior High Building

Figure 5 provides a detailed visual representation, emphasizing the strategic placement of security cameras meticulously positioned along the corridors and in close proximity to the stairway within ISAT Annex Senior High School. This deliberate arrangement aims to guarantee thorough coverage of pivotal locations, encompassing entrances, hallways, computer labs, and even the prospective server room. The illustration vividly portrays how this thoughtful placement contributes to enhancing security measures and surveillance capabilities throughout the school premises.

Miniature

In Figure 6, a concise miniature representation unveils the intricacies of the proposed network infrastructure design for ISAT Annex's Senior High Building. This visual depiction acts as a snapshot, offering a streamlined overview of the envisioned layout, highlighting key elements like strategically placed Wi-Fi access points, the efficient collapsed-core topology, and the integration of crucial security measures such as VLANs and port security. Serving as a visual guide, this miniature becomes a valuable tool for stakeholders, facilitating discussions on the proposed changes and providing insightful glimpses into the intended structure of the upcoming network enhancement

Figure 6. Miniature of Proposed Network Infrastructure Design

Figure 6 illustrates a detailed miniature model, visually representing the proposed network infrastructure at ISAT Annex Senior High School Building. This miniature provides a clear depiction of device placement, cable connections, and alignment with simulation tools, ensuring accuracy in showcasing the practical implementation of the network design within the educational setting.

Network Infrastructure Assessment: Findings and Insights from the Questionnaire

The information presented encapsulates the data gathered from an assessment of the current network infrastructure, as documented in the Network Infrastructure Design Questionnaire.

Table 4. Summary of Mean using Network Infrastructure Design Questionnaire

Criteria	Mean	Interpretation
Physical Layout	4.55	Strongly Agree
Network Map	4.57	Strongly Agree
IP Address structure	4.41	Strongly Agree
Network Security and Processes	4.60	Strongly Agree
Devices connected in the network	4.60	Strongly Agree
Miniature	4.71	Strongly Agree
Result of Simulation	4.55	Strongly Agree
Weighted Grand Mean	4.57	Strongly Agree

Tables 4 summarized the mean ratings and descriptive interpretation of the proposed network infrastructure design. The results showed that the IT Experts and ICT Coordinator strongly agree that the proposed Network Infrastructure Design of Senior High School ISAT Annex is usable and feasible in terms of its physical layout, network map, ip address structure, network security and processes, devices connected in the network, miniature, and simulation result with a general mean of 4.57.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary of Findings

The network infrastructure at ISAT Annex's Senior High Building faces challenges due to the lack of internet access, Wi-Fi connectivity, and shortage of IP addresses. To address these issues, a study titled "Network Infrastructure Design of Senior High School Building, Isabela School of Arts and Trades (ISAT) Annex" proposes a strategic design using the PPDIOO model, emphasizing planning and designing with Cisco Packet Tracer simulation. The proposed design received positive feedback from IT experts and the ICT Coordinator, particularly regarding its physical layout, network map, IP address structure, security, devices connected, simulation results, with an overall evaluation score of 4.57.

Conclusion

The evaluation of ISAT Annex Senior High School's existing network revealed significant challenges, such as the lack of internet connectivity and security vulnerabilities. In response, a well-considered network design with a collapsed-core topology, robust security measures, and strategic

Wi-Fi placement was proposed. The effectiveness of the design was validated through simulation testing, which demonstrated successful VLAN implementation, extensive Wi-Fi coverage, and secure communication. According to a questionnaire-based assessment, experts and the ICT coordinator all agreed on the efficacy of the proposed design.

In summary, the proposed network infrastructure design provided a comprehensive solution to the identified challenges, promising increased efficiency, security, and adaptability. Positive simulation testing and expert evaluations confirmed the feasibility of implementing the proposed design at ISAT Annex Senior High School Building.

Recommendation

Based on the evaluation of ISAT Annex Senior High School's existing network infrastructure and the proposed network design, several recommendations are proposed. Firstly, the implementation of the proposed network infrastructure design is advised, integrating collapsed-core topology, Wi-Fi access points, and robust security measures based on successful simulation outcomes. Secondly, organizing and securing network segments through VLAN integration is recommended to enhance performance and security. Thirdly, installing Wi-Fi access points on the second floor is suggested to ensure comprehensive internet connectivity for both students and faculty. Additionally, enforcing security measures such as VLANs and port security to mitigate internal and external threats while maintaining performance integrity is emphasized. Ensuring reliable internet access throughout the building, considering a recommended PLDT Home's 400 Mbps Fiber Unli Plan 2099, is also advised. Moreover, maintaining an updated network map for effective management, troubleshooting, and future planning is recommended, alongside optimizing the current IP addressing structure to support scalability and efficient network traffic routing. For future research, it is suggested to investigate the influence of 5G technology on educational network infrastructures, explore emerging technologies in network infrastructure to ensure adaptability, and conduct in-depth studies on the scalability of network infrastructure designs to accommodate possible expansion needs. These recommendations aim to enhance the effectiveness, security, and adaptability of the network infrastructure at ISAT Annex Senior High School while preparing for future advancements and growth.

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